

PRAGMATIC FEATURES OF INPUT DEVICES

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Annotation: Input devices and introductory words serve to complicate simple sentences. This article analyzes simple sentences that are complicated by input words and input devices.

Key words: anthropocentric paradigm, subjective assessment, introductory words, input device, intonation separation, pragmatic sign.

Input devices with specificity as a speech derivative are characterized by complicating a simple sentence. This syntactic device has its own structure and has been widely studied in linguistics. With the advent of the anthropocentric paradigm in language, the change in the view of most linguistic phenomena indicates the need to research these syntactic units from a new point of view as well.

In Uzbek linguistics, input, input devices have been researched as separately events from each other. G. Abdurakhmonov notes on the example of the work "Qutadg'u bilig" that complicated sentences with input devices were formed much earlier in Uzbek language: In "Qutadg'u bilig", some verbs (see, know, come) come introductory word task. In the old Uzbek language, the scope of use of introductory words has greatly expanded. Introductory sentences are also found in ancient Turkic. (Abdurakhmonov. p.200.)

We can also see on the example of the language of Navoi works that the range of applications of such devices has expanded in the old Uzbek language, in particular, by the 15th century. In the language of the works of Navoi S. Ashirbayev said: "The annotation and introductory phrases in the Current Uzbek literary language do not connect to the clarifying fragment being explained in the sentence through special indicators. There is no need to this. Because in our current written language, punctuation marks are used enough to indicate the grammatical attitude or separation of a syntactic phenomenon. The old Uzbek literary language had not such informational signs. (Ashirboyev. p.29.)

Regarding input devices, Fitrat also reacted: "In the middle of the conversation, a sentence or a word is entered, which doesn't have a grammatical connection with the fragments of the that sentence. That strange word or sentence is called an "introduction" The introduction corresponds to the Arabic "mu'tariza", Russian "вводное слова". (Fitrat. p.208.) Monographic research about input devices was attributed to I. Toshaliyev, and his candidate dissertation "Input constructions in the Current Uzbek literary language" reflected on the syntactic-semantic features of input devices. In linguistics entrance and input devices almost indistinguishable. There are also considerations that define the difference between a word and an input sentence in an input loop task by their location. D. Jamoliddinova defines the difference between them as an intonational separation from the main sentence, as well as displacement: "The intonational separation of introductions from the main sentence is weaker than the input phrases, while input phrases are more strongly separated from the main

sentence , therefore that the input phrases attract the attention of the reader (listener) more quickly . ” (Jamolkhonov. p.53.)

This was, undoubtedly, Aunt Larisa . (Ulugbek Hamdam. Rebellion and obedience.p. 118.)

The entrance word (*undoubtedly*) in this sentence served to express the subjective attitude of the speaker’s confidence in the information in the sentence and is pronounced with a slightly different tone.

The boy found Eldar dumb (both studies in the same class) in front of the street door. (Normurod Norqobilov . Blue lake. Stories.p.49.)

The input device in this sentence (*both studies in the same class*) serves to provide additional new information to the main point in the speech (*the fact that the boy found Eldar dumb in front of the street door*) and is pronounced with a separate tone.

The main pragmatic sign characteristic of input words and input phrases is the expression of a subjective assessment relationship in them, and in input devices such an assessment is more strongly expressed in relation to input words:

Finally, she stood up with a heavy sigh until she could not find anyone she spoke to. (Ulugbek Hamdam. Rebellion and obedience.p.30.)

In this conversation , where it is reported that the woman didn’t find a person to talk to, then stood up with a heavy sign, the introduction (*finally*) refers to the presupposition that the woman was sitting for a considerable period of time.

From the neighboring courtyard is heard howling of his brother, Alla of Rano (her mother seems to have abandoned her brother to her. (Normurod Norqobilov. Blue lake. Stories. p.51.)

In the above conversation information given about that from the neighboring courtyard her brother cried with a loud, and Rano’s Alla was heard. The introduction to the main sentence was added as a device the information “that Rano’s mother abandoning her brother” is include as a speaker estimate.

This input device also represents the presupposition that “ Rano will only say alla to her brother when her mother is not at home”. The additional information that the speaker gives in this case is also broader and more subjective than that expressed through introductory words. The additional information that the speaker gives in this case is also wider and more subjective than that expressed through introductory words.

Input devices similar to sentences in a shape, but in nature looks like an introduction. That is, it is not as grammatically attached to the main sentence, as the introductory words, and is pronounced with intonational specificity.

In the example given below, the introduction in the second sentence (hence) provides information that the action in this sentence is a conclusion drawn from the previous sentence : *Yoldor was coming in this direction and saw the Maymoq in a bush in the Chuquardara. So he will wrap himself in Karatepa again tonight. (N.Norkobilov. Enemies . p.14.)*

The input device following in the sentence also cannot come grammatical contact with the main sentence and is pronounced with a separate tone. Because input is included as additional information as an explanation of the speaker about the exclamation(uncle) used by the child: - *Uncle (he spoke this word for the first time) Are you not afraid at night ever? (Normurod Norqobilov . Blue lake. Stories.p.16.)*

Complicated simple sentences with input devices are also distinguished from compound statements. The information given in complicated simple sentences with input phrases is

similar to that in compound sentences. Because input devices can also express meanings such as annotation, cause, result, like adverbs in compound sentences. However, input devices differ from compound statements in that they do not engage grammatically with the main sentence are expressed as intonational specificity, and as additional information that appears in the speech moment:

From the gate his mother (father still not arrived) comes out .(Normurod Norqobilov . Blue lake.Stories. p.23.)

From this statement, "mother's output of the gate" is the main information, we realize that the reason for this action is "the fact that her father has not yet arrived". The information transmitter also represented a presupposition that, using an input device, "the mother does not go out to the gate while the father is at home.

We try to express this sentence in the form of a compound sentence : *His father has not yet arrived, so his mother came out of the gate.*

This statement can also be changed in the way of two simple sentences: *From the gate his mother comes out . His father has not yet arrived.* In this case, sentences become grammatical independent statements.

However, the complicated simple sentences in which the input device is involved differ in their own ways even from the two independent simple propositions. We can see this specificity that the input represents additional information that depends on the content of the main sentence of the device : *Such envy was the six day we live enjoying the blessing of socialism (no exaggeration or irony). (Erkin A'zam . The land of applause and chalpaks. Story. p.1.)*

This statement reflected the speaker's confession as a man who lives in the society of capitalism, conditions created in a socialist society. The input device is speaker's app that this recognition is not an " exaggeration or sarcasm ".

Introductory words do not enter into grammatical contact with the sentence, can be anywhere in the sentence and being separated by a comma, depending on the subjective relation being expressed. Below we can see examples of introductory words that come at the beginning of a sentence, in the middle of a sentence, and at the end of a sentence:

— *So, don't you believe I can do it ? (N.Norkobilov.Enemies. p.3.)*

Life, what is called living is, actually, that! (Ulugbek Hamdam. Rebellion and obedience. p.112.)

Now she out, when she took water from the ditch, or for sweeping the street in the mornings, only. (Isajon Sultan. Onaizorim . Story . p.23.)

Input devices cannot come at the beginning of a sentence because they represent an additional thought to the main sentence. The fact that additional information is given before the main information causes a speech disorder.

It was then that his second brother Elmurod at the institute of sculpture (now in the regional center works . Sculptor) studied .(Normurod Norqobilov . Blue lake . Stories . 35-p.)

The sentence states that " then the second brother Elmurod studied at the Institute of sculpture ". The input device manifested as the speaker's oratory need, providing further information that " Elmurod is now working in the centre of the region, a sculptor".

Input devices cannot be applied in a single manner, there will be no input device consisting of only one proposition, such units become an separated device. While the information expressed in the entries is given as an appendix, it is impossible to express in one word because it is important. In the following conversation, input device explained the reason for the information expressed in the main sentence, thus applied by extension: *The fear in the*

child's body was now replaced by wonder (The voice was coming from behind the wall). (Normurod Norqobilov . Blue lake . Stories. 42-p.)

Introductory words serve to express an additional subjective attitude of the speaker to the thought being expressed, losing their lexical meaning partially or completely. In the following conversation the introductory word was tasked with specifying the source of the thought :

In her view , her child would grow up to be an even more generous and impassioned price than Alpomish . (Isajon Sultan. Onaizorim.Story.32-p.)

The following introduction expresses the positive subjective attitude of the speaker.

Fortunately, it became impossible to fight with him. (N.Norkobilov. Enemies. Story. 16-p.)

Since input devices are manifested in the manner of the speaker's speech reserve, it seems like a speech phenomenon, but due to the fact that the ability to apply inputs comes from the speaker's lexical capacity, it would be appropriate to learn as a linguistic phenomenon.

Then I also saw such a badge on the chest of science tourists, members of the International Khan Man Men society (find out, there is such a society!). (Erkin A'zam The land of applause and chalpaks . Story . 13-p.)

From this complicated simple sentence input device, we can understand the obscurity of the society mentioned in the main sentence for the listener. The speaker wanted to highlight, that in addition to hundreds of other organizations named after Khan Man Men, there is even a society of the same name. This position shows the incomparable importance of input devices in adding to the subjective attitude of the information transmitter to the thought it represents.

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